

The Study of Life Architecture as a Discipline

CHEN, Jianhua ^{1*}

¹ Belarusian State University, Belarus

* CHEN, Jianhua is the corresponding author, E-mail: unnnnn@foxmail.com

Abstract: To sort out the historical lineage and main research status of Life Architecture; to compare the Life Architecture doctrines of the East and the West, to define the discipline of Life Architecture and to clarify the main contents of the discipline; to put forward the CLI (CHEN LIFE INDEX), the Life Development Index; to determine the scientific method for analyzing the data, to point out the direction of the development of the discipline and the direction of the research; and to promote the prosperity and development of the profession of Life Architecture.

Keywords: Life Architecture, Career Planning, Life Planning, Life Planning Studies, Life Development Index CLI (CHEN LIFE INDEX)

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1. Origin, Definition and Basic Characteristics of Life Architecture Studies

1.1 Historical origins and development of life architecture studies

Life follows the development of time, life can be scientifically planned and designed to maximize the value of life so as to obtain fame and fortune, and to achieve the goal of life.

Human beings and human-like organisms (including but not limited to robots, human-machine symbioses, etc.), which are the objects of social activities, are white paper and all beings are equal from the time they acquire the characteristics of life (artificial life) and "consciousness"; the so-called theories of sexual goodness and evilness at birth do not exist; those who inherited finances, honors, and sins at birth are the result of the additional gifts given by their external environment. Those who inherit finances, honors, and sins at birth are given them as an addition to their external environment. When a person has a sense of autonomy and has been educated and has acquired the ability to think (independently) (summarize). It is possible to intervene in a person's life, like programming a program, by manually intervening in the information and environment to which the human being is exposed, in order to achieve domination over others or to achieve one's own goals; through systematic research and planning in order to achieve the best possible model of the human being in society.

Since the origin of mankind, human beings do not have tools, will not use fire and tools, human beings are dependent on nature for life and death, born in nature, return

to nature, so there is no structure of a door, life is not independent.

With the invention of writing, the use of fire and tools, pottery and iron and culture to promote the improvement of production tools and productivity, the unprecedented prosperity of culture; human consciousness continues to awaken and the emergence of the state; this process is accompanied by the emergence of religions and a variety of schools of thought, the rulers or individuals will choose to their own most advantageous doctrine or school of thought as a guide to the independent thinking of the human consciousness continues to strengthen, the Eastern doctrine of the hundred schools of thought in the final rulers chose to respect Confucianism; at the same time, the Western religious culture, the Bible is the guide to the majority of the doctrine of the book. In the East, the Hundred Schools of Thought competed with each other, and in the end, the rulers chose to revere only Confucianism, and the Four Books and Five Classics became the guiding books for the Chinese life structure; at the same time, the Bible was the guiding book for the majority of people in the Western religious cultures.

The foundation of people's hearts is different, and the planning and development of life are not the same. The accepted theory is "Divine Mandate", the theory of destiny; both the East and the West believe that control or domination can be achieved through a certain amount of "foreshadowing, prying, or authorization". Traditional soothsayers, magicians, fortune-tellers use the media in the information gap for people to carry out the work of planning; the guiding ideology of their respective countries, different religious cultures have their own set of mature and stable incentives for people to encourage the control of the system of doctrine, grasped in the hands of a few people; the East of the "Zhouyi," the "Eight Trigrams," which is one of the masterpieces of the traditional culture and academics

represented the most advanced management of the best theories; China's ancient understanding of the "Zhouyi", "Bagua" is one of the most advanced management at the time. The best theory of the traditional culture and science represents the most advanced management at that time; China's ancient research on this aspect of the human being called "the emperor's art", "the art of employing people", "the art of the right".

After the nineteenth century, with the occurrence and development of wars, migration, trade in human beings, world shipping, the cultural renaissance of civilization, the development of democracy and the rule of law, and the great awakening of human consciousness, people gained a better understanding of "human beings". Natural human rights - immediate access at birth, equal human rights, justice and fairness. Along with the development of science and technology, the increasing frequency of production activities and globalization, there has also been a great deal of academic integration and mutation, and the dominant doctrine of human guidance has changed into the doctrine of talent management (human resource management), which is an active intervention in human beings - teaching and guidance from an early age, as well as scientific management.

In the 20th century, human resources as a doctrine has been widely accepted, the second half of the century, on the basis of human resource management developed a "talent science" said along with China's reform and opening up, shine, and achieved a very high academic status.

We can find that all the doctrines about human resource management are group doctrines, which have systematic and dynamic changes; life for the meaning of life tracing is from the beginning to the end of the activities carried out by a person, at present, there is no independent private school is to study how to trace the meaning of life, on the road of exploration of the life of the guidance or management of a comprehensive doctrine, the life structure of the science was established to summarize the past excellent experience, including the ancient, modern, Chinese and foreign excellent doctrines. This is why Life Architecture was established to summarize the excellent experience of the past, including not limited to the East, West, South, North, South, North and South, ancient and modern Chinese and foreign excellent doctrines, and scientifically codify the Life Architecture.

1.2 Disciplinary Definition of Life Architecture

Life Architecture is an emerging interdisciplinary discipline, in the broad sense, Life Architecture refers to an emerging discipline in the field of social sciences in which an individual (humanoid organism) or an organization conducts long-term planning for obtaining fame and fortune or achieving goals such as domination; in the narrow sense, Life Architecture refers to the process of guiding practice through the doctrines of Life Architecture as well as the development of the doctrine of Life Architecture itself. This

paper adopts a broad definition.

Life Architecture is an emerging discipline in the field of social sciences regarding the long-term planning of individuals (talents) or human-like organisms for their own development to achieve success and happiness and realize their goals, also known as life planning, life building, life architecture is private.

The object (field) of Life Architecture is human beings or artificial humanoid organisms, and all human beings; through scientific methods, it enables independent individuals to find ways to position themselves at different times, clarify their goals, and find the meaning of this life; and it enables the rulers to better manage the ruled, and to achieve the unanimous goals of the group, the family, the nation, the political party, or the state.

Life Architecture is an independent discipline with its own field of study - the dynamic development of life.

1.3 Basic Characteristics of Life Architecture Science

Because non-man-made life-forms in nature are independent in thought and existence, there is no continuity or natural inheritance of goals or knowledge with their predecessors; the goals or ideas or cultures will be constantly updated, and only when they reach a certain level of individuality through the use of symbols in writing or other visual symbols to pass them down, the descendants can choose to inherit them or not, which is the reason why there is no permanent regime. This is why there are no permanent regimes. We can achieve this through a systematic structure or by passing down certain cultures to achieve a long-lasting philosophy of the ruler and a long-lasting regime;

Life Architecture does not seek to generalize; we thirst for everyone to find their own meaning in this life.

Life Architecture is a systematic doctrine that attempts to systematically summarize some of the internal and external elements of life to make clear the dynamics of the various stages of our lives, so that we can have a good understanding of life and planning.

Life Architecture is a comprehensive discipline that involves environmental studies, history, talent, management, computer science, and natural science.

Life Architecture is dynamic, people are dynamic, and the key elements of life are always changing dynamically; the dynamic development of the discipline can promote the continuous development of Life Architecture.

Life Architecture believes that all human beings or humanoid organisms have equal rights to realize the value of life and find the meaning of life, and that all independent individuals are "talents".

2. Content and Function of Life Architecture

2.1 Purpose of life

The purpose of life is to experience, enjoy, and toss.

Life does not have a purpose; it is a journey to make up for missing resources, abilities or health by recognizing that you are missing (pursuing) certain abilities or resources or health in the course of your growth experience.

2.2 Key elements of the life evaluation model

A person's behavior at a particular time can be fed back through a number of key elements; Life Architecture considers these elements to be manifested in three main dimensions containing 21 key factors.

The first dimension is natural information (physical contextual basis), which summarizes 11 key factors from the underlying natural physical conditions with the individual's physical indicator data: gender, age, place of birth, height, weight, hearing, vision, health status, disability or not, psychological status, and orthopedic status.

The second dimension is kinetic information (learning kinetic), which is described in terms of the output of a person's behavior or the resources and capabilities at their disposal. It contains six factors such as learning ability, education, specialization, job, income and skills.

The third dimension is the kinetic factor (learning kinetic), which is evaluated through an individual's value output, work output or career achievement, and contains four factors: contribution, literature, influence, and intellectual achievement.

Indicator System of Life Integration Competency Scoring and Evaluation Index	
Nature information (physical environment basis) x 1	Gender x1(1)
	Age x1(2)
	Birthplace x 1(3)
	Height x 1(4)
	Weight x 1(5)
	Listening x 1 (6)
	Visual acuity x 1(7)
	Health status x 1 (8)
	Disabled or not x 1(9)
	Mental state x 1 (10)
	Corrective status x1(11)
Kinetic energy information (learning about kinetic energy) x2	Academic qualifications x 2 (1)
	Specialization x2(2)
	Income x2(3)
	Work x2(4)
	Skills x2(5)
	Learning capacity x 2 (6)
Value information (value outputs)x3	Contribution x 3 (1)
	Literature x3(2)
	Impact x 3(3)
	Intellectual achievement x 3(4)

The three main dimensions are proposed to realize the data representation of life development ability at a certain period of time, and the index derived from the comprehensive scoring of the 21 key factors is the Chen Life Index (CLI); through the scoring and grading of the 21 key elements, the optimal life development index of the current independent individual is derived. The index analyzes the developmental status of the individual, and through the 21-element "analysis list", it gives clear guidance on the enhancement of the key elements, so that the individual can achieve a benign balance or development between multiple key elements.

Through the 21 key elements can be combined to form important descriptive labels of life such as career, family,

behavioral style, behavioral preference, learning ability, career, influence, networking, social contribution, vitality, mindset, skills, wealth, education, family, love, friends and so on.

The meaning of life is to realize the life purpose of an independent individual, balancing the key elements of the life evaluation model Life Development Index CLI indicators, the meaning of the life structure is to assist you to organize and clarify the positioning of the missing points, for reasonable prediction and practical guidance.

2.3 Types of Learning Inquiry for the Development of Life

The most basic of life's reserves is knowledge learning and acquisition, and we learn new things all the time from our teenage years to our old age. Life Architecture Learning considers three types of learning:

- 1) Mentor-apprentice mode, automatic or passive acceptance of other people's knowledge, this mode is generally applicable to the inheritance of articulation, training, skills upgrading, academic education and other ways.
- 2) Active self-learning model, in which the independent individual learns on his/her own initiative in order to explore and solve problems. This model is applied when the independent individual is actively acquiring knowledge, skills, and information.
- 3) Socialized information model, in the case of mass media, the individual is in the middle of the communication or the receiving end of the media, the independent individual can easily access to information or the information channel is blocked, and trigger the independent individual to make a learning or revolution, use the poor information to conduct business activities, deception and other behaviors.

2.4 Growth model

Life Architecture believes that all beings are equal under the sky, and all independent individuals are equal talents; there is no essential difference between the "talent body", and the differentiation comes from the investment of time and energy as well as the degree of concentration; Life Architecture believes that the life growth model is divided into:

- 1) Generalist model, a growth model that follows the natural growth patterns and does behaviors consistent with the behavioral trajectory of the age group, according to the conventions of the group (community, state, nation, family); in the generalist growth model talents can be divided into specialists and generalists; specialists are those with specific skills or a bias towards a specialized field, and generalists refer to those with a composite of multiple competencies and involvement in multiple fields.
- 2) Elite people mode, different from the ordinary people mode, elite refers to those in the cutting-edge field to maintain the lead, or in a particular field to maintain the first place, in the professional field has a very high authority and discourse, or has some absolute power; according to the elite struggle towards the course of the chosen mode is called elite people mode.

Absolute power includes: wealth, right, power, status, word-of-mouth honor, material information, physical power (voice, organism, curves, beauty). Absolute power can be acquired in two ways, the first is the natural mode: innate

possession, acquired by inheritance, and through practice in accordance with the laws of nature; and the second is the differentiated mode: acquired by poor information, acquired by deception, long-term concentration, and aided by external tools.

1) Differential mode, by comparing with the surrounding around the social circle in the social circle with 90% of the people do not have the same way of behavior or has the information difference ability or has the unconventional collar social person certain absolute five or more absolute power.

2) Hybrid modes, also known as hybrid mech-bio modes; independent individuals using a combination of multiple other modes in the same time slot or in combination is called a hybrid mode.

Life is dynamic, and different growth models are used at different times; different models are used at different times within the same time period, and as differentiated individuals come into existence, they will deduce their own developmental models; it is important to note that our theories are always evolving and being updated.

2.5 Group division

The independent individual is the most basic unit of group division, the independent individual has his own independent consciousness, behavioral style, the person's whole life is moving forward independently, the person spends much of his life alone;

The family is the second dimension of group division, the family is a harmonious and natural unit, individuals through love, blood and other factors to form a family, to resist risks, to learn to live and grow together, to assume the role of maintaining education and life, and to guide and educate the growth of independent individuals.

Other groups of three or more people, such as political parties, nations, and nationalities, are collectively referred to as other groups, which share a common goal or identity, and are aggregations of temporal, spatial, and geographic locations that play a role.

2.6 Classification of occupations

Occupational dimensions can be categorized according to class: officials, political parties, educational and academic personnel, businessmen, soldiers, workers, farmers, and others; a clear occupational orientation will bring good assistance in the choice of growth patterns.

2.7 The Life Architecture task

2.7.1 mandates

Discipline construction, from the construction of theoretical foundation of disciplines to the combination of theory and practice, to realize the comprehensive development of disciplines; talent cultivation, the

introduction of disciplinary talents and fringe combination of disciplinary talents, the cultivation and introduction of talents in specialized fields, and the development of teaching and academic research in universities, colleges and research institutes; eco-construction, guiding the development of the Life Architecture industry, the creation of industry companies, the authentication and cultivation of talents in the industry, and the ecological construction related to the life architecture science. Ecological construction, guiding the development of life architecture industry, creating industry companies, certification and training of industry talents, and ecological construction related to life architecture.

2.7.2 Industry Association Content

Development of Life Architecture teaching materials; updating of Life Architecture theory system; maintenance of Life Architecture Society members; development of guidance planning for the industry, establishment of Life Architecture companies; vocational training and certification of Life Architects; regular organization of industry summits.

2.7.3 Life Architecture Learning Reality Integration Work.

Human Resource Planner, Human Resource Management, Career Planning Manager, Life Architecture Data Institute, Life Architect Certification and Training.

2.8 Functions of Life Architecture Science

Evaluation function: to make a scientific evaluation of life.

Predictive identification function: Predictive guidance for the direction of the next step in life, giving scientific guidance advice.

Guidance Planning: Scientific guidance planning for the analysis sheets that have been given.

3. Research Methods in Life Architecture

3.1 Occupational case study method

The best guide in life is a role model; Life Architecture starts from the dimension of occupation, summarizes the development trajectory of outstanding people in various occupations, analyzes outstanding individuals through the CLI index, and summarizes outstanding people in various industries in China and the West as reference objects for independent individuals.

3.2 Big Data Research Methodology

The career dimension big data is collected according to independent individuals, and combined with AI neural network training to derive the most compatible life development index CLI model for independent individuals.

1) Collection of Independent Individual 21 Key Element Big Data by Occupational Dimension.

2) Trained career dimension model, life critical moment model according to AI neural network

3) The scoring of new independents according to the resulting scientific model guides production practices.

4. Future development of the discipline

Life Architecture is an emerging interdisciplinary discipline, which is still in the period of foundation creation. Talent resources, industry resources have not been configured, and the combination with practice is not strong enough, the development of the discipline and the industry needs a long time to develop. The development of the discipline in the next 15 years needs to operate from the following steps.

1. The Association for the Study of Life Architecture was established, and the development of teaching materials such as Introduction to Life Architecture and the Concise Course on Life Architecture was carried out in accordance with the contents of the "Association" of disciplines.

2. Regular industry summits are held to guide the healthy and orderly development of Life Architecture, and to strengthen the training and introduction of professionals.

3. Establishment and maintenance of industry newspapers and websites

4. Life Institutions Theory its study and its related professional qualification and training

5. Establishment of a specialized company whose main business is life architecture

Life architecture science for independent individuals to achieve goals, complete the design of life, the group to achieve the rule to play a function; the ultimate goal of the doctrine is to let the world live a good life.

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Author Contributions

All studies in this paper were conducted and headed by Chen, Jianhua

About the Authors

CHEN, Jianhua

Born in June 1995, male with the character Lian and the name Dongyang Jushi, born in Zhenkang, Yunnan. He holds a Master's degree in Economics from the National University of Belarus and is a Senior Software Engineer. He mainly engages in research in enterprise economics, artificial intelligence software development, and (career planning) life architecture.

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